

THE INFLUENCE OF CURE CONDITION AND TEST TEMPERATURE
ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF GRAPHITE/BISMALEIMIDE

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ABSTRACT

In the present investigation on a carbon fibre reinforced modified bismaleimide (T800/V398) it is shown that the matrix flexural stiffness decreases by 52% up to a temperature of 250°C. As a result of this the modulus of the unidirectional material decreases in fibre direction only by 6%, whereas transverse to the fibre the modulus decreases by 19%. In terms of strength unidirectional (UD) material transverse to the fibre and two different quasi-isotropic laminates were characterized.

The strength transverse to the fibres generally decreases at increasing test temperature. The transverse fracture strain, however, reaches a minimum value at intermediate temperatures before it increases again upon approaching the maximum (post)cure temperature. This behaviour mainly is the result of a reduction of the strain at interface failure at intermediate temperatures followed by a clear increase at higher temperatures. The transverse strength and fracture strain generally is higher if higher (post)cure temperatures are applied. The strength of the quasi-isotropic laminate (+45/90/-45/0)_s first increases considerably (16%) up to 100°C after which a decrease up to 250°C (6%) takes place. The strength of the stronger (-45/0/+45/90)_s laminate is less effected by the temperature.

KEYWORDS: CFRP; matrix, bismaleimide; high temperature; interface; fracture

1. INTRODUCTION

In the past years much effort was done to develop resin systems for high temperature applications, e.g. polyimide and bismaleimide resin systems. A lot of work still has to be done to understand the high temperature properties of CFRP with these resin systems.

The present investigation on a carbon fibre reinforced modified bismaleimide (T800/V398, delivered by BP) intends to give a contribution to this understanding.

It is evident, that the properties of the composite are influenced by the properties of the fibres, matrix and interface (or better interphase). In the temperature range of RT to 300°C the properties of the fibre are hardly effected. For this reason a variation of composite properties in this temperature range is mainly caused by the variation of matrix and interphase properties. Thus matrix and interphase dominated properties will vary considerably and fibre dominated properties to a less degree. This is the reason that the flexural strength of the unidirectional material transverse to the fibre is investigated. Further a more fibre dominated property, the strength of two quasi-isotropic laminates was determined.

2. MATERIALS

Laminates were produced in a pressclave at 190°C (for 6 h), a pressure of 700 kPa and with vacuum in the vacuum bag. The temperature was reached after a heat up cycle with 3°C/min, whereas cooling was established at a rate of 2°C/min. Crossply 0/90_n/0 laminates with n=4 and n=8 contained many cracks after cooling down from the cure temperature of 190°C. The laminates were produced on top of a steel tool plate (covered with a plastic foil) and below an aluminium top plate (5 mm thick) which is placed inside the vacuum bag. Recent investigations on PMR-15 materials [1] have shown that transverse cracking in a cross-ply laminate can be prevented if the laminate is produced between zero-expansion material. For this reason 0/90/0 laminates were produced between two graphite/epoxy

quasi-isotropic plates. The number of cracks in these crossply laminates was considerable lower than in the conventionally cured crossply laminate. Two different postcure cycles (on free standing laminates) were used:

1. 4h at 227 °C and 4h at 246°C (advised post-cure cycle, cycle 1)
2. 4h at 227°C, 4h at 246°C and 4h at 270°C (cycle 2)

The produced material was stored in a desiccator to minimize moisture uptake. Some pure resin plates (cured according to cycle 1) delivered by BP were used to study the pure resin properties.

3. RESULTS

A complete overview of the cure behaviour and mechanical properties is given elsewhere [2]. In this report only the results on pure resin properties and on the unidirectional and quasi-isotropic laminates are given.

3.1 PROPERTIES OF PURE RESIN

Pure resin specimens cut from plates delivered by BP were tested in flexure to determine the modulus as a function of the test temperature. Three different specimens were tested (in the linear elastic range only) at stepwise increasing temperatures. The flexural modulus decreases from $E_m = 4.99$ GPa at RT to $E_m = 2.39$ GPa at 250°C which is a decrease of 52%. The decrease as a function of the temperature is about linear. The flexural modulus thus clearly decreases before the glass-transition temperature is reached which for the postcured material measures $T_g = 300^\circ\text{C}$ according to the data sheet [3]. Because of the little amount of pure resin available the influence of the temperature on the strength and fracture strain could not be determined.

3.2 PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE

3.2.1 INFLUENCE OF THE TEMPERATURE ON THE TENSILE MODULUS OF UNIDIRECTIONAL MATERIAL

The tensile modulus was measured on specimens out of the laminate (0)₈ in fibre direction as well as perpendicular to the fibre direction. As expected the modulus in fibre direction decreases only little at increasing temperature. The tensile modulus decreases from $E_{//} = 176.0$ GPa at RT to $E_{//} = 164.8$ GPa at 250°C (a decrease of 6.4% at 250°C in comparison with the RT value). The modulus transverse to the fibre direction, however, decreases considerably at increasing test temperature. At 250°C the tensile transverse modulus decreases by 19% in comparison with the RT value ($E_{\perp} = 8.62$ GPa at 250°C in comparison with $E_{\perp} = 10.7$ GPa at RT).

3.2.2 FLEXURAL TRANSVERSE UNIDIRECTIONAL PROPERTIES

The flexural properties (transverse modulus and flexural transverse strength and fracture strain) are determined on 25-27 specimens out of the laminate (0)₁₆ at the different test temperatures. The transverse modulus was determined with the aid of the registered load deflection curves and the following equation [4]:

$$E_{\perp} = L^3 m / (4bd^3) \quad (1)$$

where m is the slope of the load deflection curve and L , b , d the span, width and thickness of the specimen respectively [4]. The flexural modulus is somewhat lower than the tensile modulus. The decrease in modulus at increasing temperature is however similar. The transverse modulus depends on the maximum (post) cure temperature. At RT the influence is small; if the test temperature exceeds the (post) cure temperature and approaches the glass transition temperature, however, the modulus is severely reduced [2]. The maximum transverse strain at specimen failure $\epsilon_{f,\perp}$ can be calculated with the aid of:

$$E_{f,\perp} = 6 Dd/L^2 \quad (2)$$

where D is the maximum deflection, d (= 2 mm) is the specimen thickness, whereas L is the span (L = 32 mm) [4]. In this way the maximum strain at fracture of the different specimens is determined. The fracture data at the different temperatures is fitted to two parameter Weibull distributions given by:

$$F = 1 - \exp - (\epsilon_{f,\perp} / \hat{\epsilon}_{f,\perp})^a \quad (3)$$

where F is the probability of specimen failure at a maximum strain of $\epsilon_{f,\perp}$ and the two Weibull parameters $\hat{\epsilon}_{f,\perp}$ and a are the characteristic transverse fracture strain and the shape parameter respectively. The probability of failure for the different specimens can be calculated with:

$$F = j/(N+1) \quad (4)$$

where j is the fracture order number (from the list of tested specimens listed in increasing order of strength) and N is the number of specimens tested at the respective temperature.

The fracture data for the material without postcure (cured for 6h at 190°C) is indicated in figure 1a for experiments performed at RT, 100°C and 200°C. Best fit two parameter Weibull distributions are determined with the aid of linear regression and least square analysis for all data sets. These Weibull distributions are presented by the straight lines in figure 1a. Figure 1a makes clear that from RT to 100°C the transverse fracture strain decreases but that at 200°C the transverse fracture strain rises above the values at RT. The material postcured according to cycle 1 (figure 1b) and cycle 2 (figure 1c) generally show a similar behaviour: a minimum transverse fracture strain at intermediate temperatures.

The characteristic fracture strain for the different cured materials is presented in figure 2a as a function of the test temperature. It shows that at higher cure temperatures a higher characteristic fracture strain is reached. Further at increasing test temperature the characteristic strain decreases. Before, however, the test temperature approaches the cure temperature a minimum fracture strain is reached after which the fracture

strain increases. The characteristic transverse strength shows a similar dependency on the temperature as indicated in figure 2b (except for very high test temperatures where the reduction in strength rather continues).

3.2.3 TENSILE BEHAVIOUR OF QUASI-ISOTROPIC LAMINATES

Two different quasi-isotropic laminates were tested at increasing temperatures. These are the laminates $(+45/90/-45/0)_S$ and $(-45/0/+45/90)_S$ postcured according to cycle 1. Load displacement curves were registered during the crosshead-controlled ($V_{cr} = 2$ mm/min) experiments. The tensile strength of the laminate $(-45/0/+45/90)_S$ decreases (see fig. 3) slightly at increasing temperature. The strength of the laminate with the orientation $(+45/90/-45/0)_S$ is smaller than for the the other quasi-isotropic laminate. Peculiar for this laminate is that from RT to 100°C the strength increases by 16%, whereas above 100°C (at 250°C) the strength decreases (by 6%).

4. DISCUSSION

Mechanical properties can be divided in fibre and matrix dominated properties. It is evident that the changing properties of the matrix at increasing temperatures mainly influences the matrix dominated properties. Thus the decrease of the matrix modulus by 52% up to 250°C only reduces the modulus of the unidirectional material in fibre direction by 6.4% and transverse to the fibre direction by 19%.

The transverse fracture strain in flexure is influenced by the matrix as well as the interface properties. The fracture data for transverse flexure gives a qualitative indication of the strength of the interface at increasing temperature. The model developed for transverse cracking under tension [5, 6] can in principle also be applied to transverse cracking in flexure. The influence of defects and interface strength according to this model is presented in figure 4. Indicated is schematically the two parameter Weibull distribution and the influence of the defects and the interface. The biggest defects are responsible for the low strain failures (in the tail of the Weibull distribution),

whereas the top of the Weibull distribution rather reflects the interface properties (or ultimate matrix properties).

Thus it is easy to understand that a reduction of the effectiveness of defects (as a result of higher temperatures making the matrix more ductile) shifts the lower part of the Weibull distribution to the right (higher fracture strains). This leads to an increased fracture strain for the first failures and to a steeper Weibull distribution (larger value of a). An increased interface strength leads to a larger shift of the top of the Weibull distribution than for the tail resulting in a decrease of the shape parameter a (a less steep distribution).

Now we can estimate the influence of test temperature on the strength of the interface with the aid of the Weibull distributions for the different test temperatures and differently cured materials (figure 1). The material cured at 190°C (figure 1a) shows a decrease of interface strength at 100°C in comparison with RT-experiments. The reduction in interface strength even overrules (for the first cracks to occur) the positive influence of increased ductility. At 200°C the interface improves (also in comparison with the RT results) leading to higher fracture strains mainly at the top of the distribution. The improvement in the tail because of increased ductility is smaller. The other two materials postcured at 246°C (cycle 1, figure 1b) and postcured at 270°C (cycle 2, figure 1c) show in principle the same effect. At an increased temperature there is a clear reduction of the strain at interface failure leading to a steeper Weibull distribution. At a further increase of the test temperature the strain at interface failure increases again leading to a smaller shape parameter.

It is interesting to see that the two quasi-isotropic laminates show a reverse dependency (figure 5) of the strength on the temperature in comparison with the transverse flexure strain (figure 1b). From RT to 100°C there is an increase (for the -45/0/+45/90_g laminate only a minor), whereas from 100°C to 250°C the strength decreases. The reason for this behaviour is not investigated yet. Further information, e.g. about the damage starting to develop at the specimens edge, will help to answer this question.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Experiments up to temperatures of 250° to 300°C have shown that matrix properties and matrix and interface dominated properties change considerably. The flexural modulus of the matrix was found to decrease by 52% up to a temperature of 250°C. As a result of this at 250°C the modulus of the unidirectional laminate decreases by 6% in fibre direction and 19% transverse to the fibres. At increasing temperatures (up to 100°C) the transverse fracture strain of the 190°C cured material initially decreases, followed by a an increase up to 200°C.

From the Weibull distributions for the (flexural) fracture strain and making use of a model for transverse cracking it could be concluded that the decrease in fracture strain is caused by a reduction in interface strength. The improvement at still higher temperatures is caused by an increase in interface strength.

A postcure improves the transverse properties in terms of fracture strain and strength (not in modulus) and the improvement sustains in the range of temperatures investigated. The tensile strength of quasi-isotropic laminates first increases up to 100°C (laminate (+45/90/-45/0)_S by 1%; laminate (-45/0/+45/90)_S by 16%) after which at 250°C a decrease of about 6% occurs. This behaviour is expected to be the result of a complicated interaction between first damage (first ply failure) and the strength of the load carrying 0° plies.

6. REFERENCES

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Figure 1: Transverse fracture strain data for the different test temperatures for
 a) the material cured at 190°C
 b) cure cycle 1
 c) cure cycle 2

Figure 2: Characteristic fracture strain a) and characteristic strength b) in flexure as a function of the test temperature for the different cured material

Figure 3: Tensile strength of specimens out of two different quasi-isotropic laminates as a function of the test temperature

Figure 4: Influence of defects and interface strength on the Weibull distribution for transverse flexure based on a model for transverse cracking [5, 6]